

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE USE OF NATIONAL MOVEMENT GAMES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES IN PRIMARY GRADES

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ABSTRACT

The thesis scientifically analyzes the pedagogical and psychological foundations of the use of national movement games in physical education classes in primary grades. The impact of national games on the formation of physical, psychomotor, volitional and social competencies is substantiated on the basis of empirical data. According to the results of the study, games such as "Uloq-k'pkari", "Chillak", "Arqon tarisht", "Kiz-quvdi" are effective tools for developing students' agility, dexterity, coordination, psychological stability and social interaction.

Introduction

The use of national movement games in physical education lessons plays an important role in instilling in the younger generation the historical heritage, traditions and educational values of the Uzbek people. Today, the role of national games not only in physical development, but also in the formation of skills such as psychological stability, social communication, emotional balance, and teamwork is at the center of scientific research.

Objective

To scientifically substantiate the pedagogical and psychological effectiveness of the use of national movement games in primary grades and develop methodological recommendations.

Tasks:

1. Analyze the historical and pedagogical foundations of national games in the process of physical education.
2. Identify the characteristics of the physical development of primary school students.
3. Develop a scientific and methodological model for the implementation of national games in physical education lessons.
4. Evaluate the effectiveness of the use of national games in physical education lessons based on a pedagogical experiment.
5. To determine the changes in psychomotor, social and national identification indicators of students.
6. To develop practical recommendations based on the results of the study.

Methodology

Theoretical methods:

- literature analysis,
- historical and pedagogical analysis,
- conceptual modeling,
- comparative analysis.

Empirical methods:

- pedagogical observation,
- diagnostics and tests (coordination, agility, speed),
- interviews and questionnaires,
- experiments using game methods,
- assessment by psychomotor development criteria.

Statistical methods:

- percentage indicators,
- mathematical and statistical processing,
- variation analysis.

Results

The study showed that:

The game “Chillak” develops coordination, quick decision-making and spatial thinking;

- “Tug of war” strengthens physical strength, willpower and teamwork;
- “Uloq-k’pkari” (adapted version) – develops speed, coordination and strategic thinking;
- “Kiz-kuvdi” – increases endurance and agility.

According to empirical observations, lessons using national games:

- develop mutual respect among students,
- communicative culture,
- healthy competition,
- interest in sports,
- strengthen self-management skills.

Conclusion

The use of national movement games in primary grades:

- promotes a healthy lifestyle;
- activates physical development;
- strengthens psychological stability;
- forms social competencies;
- ensures the continuity of values.

National games are of great pedagogical importance in the educational process not only as a physical development tool, but also as a socio-psychological educational tool.

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